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THE USE OF COOPERATIVE LEARNING IN THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE DENTISTS

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ВИКОРИСТАННЯ МЕТОДУ КООПЕРАТИВНОГО НАВЧАННЯ ПРИ ПРОФЕСІЙНІЙ ПІДГОТОВЦІ МАЙБУТНІХ СТОМАТОЛОГІВ

Abstract.

Socio-economic changes that are taking place in the country today define the requirements for professional training of future health care professionals. The reform of higher education in Ukraine poses the problem of the quality of training of a new generation of professionals who have the latest information, are able to obtain it and use it effectively for efficient professional activity; have organisational skills, ability to manage people in extreme situations, be able to work in teams, solve complex professional problems and take responsibility for decision making. Professional training of future dentists cannot be limited only to the acquisition of professional competences, purposeful formation and development of professional and personal qualities that ensure the effectiveness of the activities. The holistic professional training requires the creation of effective educational conditions for the development of the personality of the future professionals. To ensure a high quality professional training to the future activity permits the use in the educational process of modern models, methods and forms of learning, among which a significant position is taken by the cooperative learning or training in collaboration.

Анотація.

Соціально-економічні зміни, що відбуваються сьогодні в країні, визначають суворі вимоги до професійної підготовки майбутніх фахівців охорони здоров'я. Реформування вищої освіти в Україні направлене на підвищення якості підготовки фахівців нового покоління, які вмело володіють новітньою інформацією, уміють її отримувати та ефективно використовувати для ефективної професійної діяльності; володіти організаторськими здібностями, вмінням керувати людьми в екстремальних ситуаціях, працювати у команді, вирішувати складні професійні проблеми та брати відповідальність за прийняття рішень. Професійна підготовка майбутніх лікарів-стоматологів не може обмежуватися лише набуттям професійних компетентностей, цілеспрямованим формуванням й розвитком професійних та особистісних якостей, що забезпечують ефективність діяльності. Цілісна професійна підготовка потребує створення ефективних освітніх умов для розвитку особистості майбутніх фахівців. Забезпечити високу якість професійної підготовки до майбутньої діяльності дозволяє використання в освітньому процесі сучасних моделей, методів та форм навчання, серед яких значне місце займає кооперативне навчання або навчання у співпраці.

Keywords: *method, training, competence, education, dentistry.*

Ключові слова: *метод, навчання, компетентність, освіта, стоматологія.*

Introduction. The processes of globalization, democratization and informatization that are currently taking place in society determine the requirements for the professional training of future health care professionals [1]. A teacher of higher education should not only master the system of scientific knowledge, but also be able to perceive and use in practice new progressive ideas, to master the skills of self-study, carry out professional tasks, take responsibility for taking effective solutions for non-standard occupational situations and be competitive in the labour market [2]. The medical education must provide high quality training of health care professionals, who must not only be proficient in their specialty, but also to master the necessary competencies to solve complex medical problems, to be able to adapt to new changes, to understand the basics of insurance, economics, law.

The research goal: studying the impact of cooperative education on the development of professional competence of the future professionals in the field of health care.

Materials and methods: theoretical-analysis of scientific literature to determine the status of the investigated problem; practical-testing, interviews, supervision, tests to determine the feasibility of using cooperative education for vocational training of future health care professionals.

Results obtained. Cooperative learning is aimed at optimising the educational process and democratising the relationship between the educator and the trainees. Among the basic principles of this training is the transition from monologic presentation of the material to a demonstration of the possibilities of obtaining the necessary data in the process of active cognitive activity from the available resources [3]. Creation of a comfortable learning environment where each educational participant feels psychologically satisfied with the learning process and acquiring the knowledge needed for their future professions; creation of a collaborative atmosphere; the transition to a dialogue-based cooperation between the instructor and future professors, and between them, which leads to the formation of communicative competences: the ability to assert your point of view, to listen actively to the co-worker, to find a common solution, etc. [4]. The experience of cooperative learning in the educational process of higher education institutions shows that education learners work with satisfaction in the cooperative mode, learning the educational material is easier and more effective. In cooperative learning, the students work in small groups,

sharing a common goal and solving the problem collectively, make decisions jointly and bear individual responsibility for each individual member, have different levels of capability to achieve individual success [5]. Among the main methods of cooperative learning are «team training», «small group work» and «pair work», where significant emphasis is placed on group goals and the success of the whole group or pair, which can only be achieved as a result of each team member (pair) working independently in constant interaction with other members of the same group on a certain topic, problem, or issue to be studied [6]. The job of each educator is not only to do something together, but also to learn something together, so that each member of the group (pair) acquired the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities, and at the same time, the whole group must know what each one has achieved separately.

Conclusion. Thus, using the cooperative teaching method in professional training of future dentists creates conditions for comprehensive development of students and formation of professionally important characteristics through continuous communication between all participants, the students are encouraged to be creative and collaborative, to participate actively in teamwork, and to be personally responsible for their decisions.

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